

The formation of children's literature and common ideas in American and Uzbek children's prose

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Annotation: The article talks about the emergence and formation factors of Uzbek and American children's literature as a science. Similarities and differences of the children's literature of the two nations are analyzed in terms of the theme of the works created for children.

Key words: children's literature, folklore, moral books, revolutions of the Enlightenment, national renaissance, didactic, fantastic, idyllic, sister notions, domestic Utopia.

“Children's literature - sensitive literature. Children's literature is the beginning of adult literature which we know... Children's writers with their works are the creators of great literature. This literature is the literature which demands respect, honor... The heart of a child is like that. It cannot be broken. It always needs attention. Only then will it be satisfied. It is affectionate. Only then will it become the fruit of your love, follows your footsteps”.¹

Children's literature is an important part of the literature of all nations because it shapes the minds and worldviews of future generations. The tradition of creating a special literature for children is manifested in the form of an important spiritual need of society's development. Although Uzbek children's literature has come into existence in the written literature of the East on the basis of works classified by such names as "pandnom", "mavizatnama", "nasihatnama", “moral books”, etc., it is recognized that its formation is closely related to enlightenment - reforms of the school-educational system.²

In the development of Uzbek children's literature, first of all, social reality, then folk oral creativity, didactic literature and classical children's reading are considered important phenomena. Children's literature, which appeared in Uzbek literature in the context of the

¹ (Fozilov, 2010)

² (Oxunjon Safarov, Rahmatulla Barakayev, Bashorat Jamilova, 2020)

revolutions of the Enlightenment, national renaissance, and modernist literature, is a unique and unusual direction, which first appeared as a phenomenon, a revolution, and then developed as an independent science.

The miraculous power of children's literature forms benignity, patriotism, artistic taste in young hearts, as well as encourages to have a positive and creative attitude towards life and the whole world. As the great writers of the XIX century V. G. Belinsky, N.G.Chernishevsky and N. A.Dobrolyubov claimed, the fiction stories which cannot only educate but also can reflect the scenes from the real fast-paced life, and help young readers enjoy aesthetic pleasure in the stories, are very necessary.

The emergence of Uzbek children's literature is mainly led by four factors:

- As mentioned, classic didactic literature, i.e. religious and secular literature: pandnoms, moral, educational works (Kaykovus, Sa'diy, Jamiy, Navoiy) "moral books" (Savodi talim, single verses, chstons);

- Folklore, i.e. children's songs, lullabies, and nursery rhymes;

- Literature of the world and sister nations (For example, Grimm brothers, A.S. Pushkin, I.A. Krylov, N. Tolstoy);

- Pedagogical treatises and children's works of modern enlighteners (Behbudi's "Kitab ut-aftoli", "Tarbiyat ut-atfol"; Avlani's "Turkish Gulistan or Ethics", "School Gulistan", "First Teacher", "Second Teacher"); "Light literature", "Reading book", "Reading book" by Hamza; "Reading" by Fitrat; "Kiz bola or Khalida" by S. Aini).

In America, along with "the Bible" and "the New England Primer," "Bunyan's" "The Pilgrim's Progress," "Watts's Hymns," and "Divine Songs," and including "Janeway's Token for Children" with American modifications, were the main works of acceptable reading in the early 18th century. There were several such stories of religious youngsters, warnings from serious and frightening divines, and wisdom passed down from mother to daughter or father to son.³

'American children's literature' didn't exist during the period of the 18th century because America was still colonial and London was the center of culture. However, there

³ (Comparative Children's Literature: The United States of America, 2016)

were printers in Boston and Philadelphia. British works were frequently Americanized by making little changes to minor elements.

There were two primary categories of American children's books throughout the 100 years following Newbery's death: didactic and commercial. They were created for young people who could be considered "respectable," for future middle-class masters and misses. In the 1860s, "Alice's Adventures in Wonderland" and "Water Babies" were two popular fantasies.

"The Era of the Child" ran from 1865 until 1914. This was influenced by a number of intellectual trends: a) Nostalgia (because the second half of the 19th century was dramatically different from the first half; b) The Civil War changed everything (urbanization); c) Fascination With The Future (there was the laying of the transatlantic cable, the completion of the Union Pacific Railroad, telephones, electric lights, first flight, and children were symbols of the future); d) Progress Through Recapitulation (nearly all the big name American writers of this time were often on steam ships, crossing the Atlantic and were early adopters of tech, and this seems contradictory since they were writing about childhood idylls, but adults of this time were able to regress to the psychic age of their children in order to write for them); e) Changing Attitudes About Childhood (children were less indulged before this era, which became a lot more middle class with free time for the masses); f) New Interest In Child Raising Practices (parents were careful about not sullyng their children's innocence, the first paediatric clinic was established in NYC, parents started to think about how they were parenting and realized that 'parents' were responsible for children's needs); g) The Child As Public Figure (before now children were mostly raised in rural areas but now they were the center of American cultural life, vehicles for nostalgia, symbols of the future, put on stage for the first time. No longer seen and not heard.)

Historical fiction frequently centers on emancipation from slavery. Tom Sawyer and Black Beauty are from the 1870s. There were two main categories of American children's literature prior to Mark Twain's *The Adventures of Tom Sawyer*: spiritual memoirs of miserable but holy waifs, and Aesopian fables of Good and Bad children (later formalized in the Sunday school narrative). However, Clemens also took the first style of narrative and flipped it on its head, praising the Bad Boy. The second kind of narrative is also parodied

by Tom Sawyer. Sometimes, a purely comical goal was concealed by an overtly didactic one. The 1920s was a great decade for American literature, whereas it was going through a down period over in Britain. There were now specialist courses for children's librarians and the first children's editor was appointed by Macmillan of New York in 1919. Other American publishers followed.

The finest American literature written between the wars tended to focus on the War of Independence, the European colonization of the East Coast, and the migration to the West. White Anglo-Saxon perspectives were expressed because this group was the author.⁴ Since 1945, picture books have flourished. The printing industry has seen significant technical improvements, and the value of books for young children is becoming increasingly recognized. The critics consider Maurice Sendak to be the greatest author of the last hundred years or so. It took some time though for excellent American children's literature to come out of the more welcoming environment. Some of the early Newbery Medal winners aren't actually all that great.

Children's literature tended to be idyllic or subtly amusing around the middle of the 20th century. Children's novels from the 1950s tended to be tranquil. There was a trend toward problem-focused novels in the 1970s and 1980s. As the Cold War lingered, people were concerned that a bomb could wipe out the whole planet. Of course, this was a threat that had never existed before. Fantasy has flourished alongside the stories that focus on solving problems.⁵

American children's literature upholds the ideals of a domestic utopia, whereas Uzbek children's literature encourages children to mature. This occurred after World War II, when Americans had been deprived of the comforts of domesticity for several decades due to economic hardship and conflict. American children's literature was remarkably idyllic even in the postwar years. Then authors like Patricia MacLachlan and Katherine Paterson appeared. Their narratives abruptly turned away from Arcadia. Sometimes Virginia Hamilton is cited as the first notable black children's author. Of all "black women and black writers to have received" the Newbery Medal, she was unquestionably the first.

⁴ (Jumaboyev, 2013)

⁵ (Behrens, 2015)

In conclusion, comparing the history of American and Uzbek children's literature some similar and special features can be noticed. The children's literatures of both nations were developed as a science at the beginning of XX century and influenced by world and sister nations' literature. However, while Uzbek children's literature was mainly didactic, the common topics of American literature were idyllic, about escape from slavery, discrimination, and the ideals of domestic Utopia.

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